

EDUCATIONAL INNOVATION AND TECHNOLOGY

EDUCATIONAL INNOVATION AND TECHNOLOGY: A NEED FOR INTEGRATION

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ABSTRACT: This paper aims to discuss why and how teaching practices and technologies need to be integrated, at all levels, to improve learners meaningful learning. A first attempt to define pedagogical innovation is presented, with a reference to Creative Class Room framework (CCR). In the CCR framework, innovation is seen as an intentional activity, occurring in a specific social, economic, technological, organizational and cultural context, designed to address unsolved problems and involving complex interactions between various actors who actively seek to learn from one another. From this point of view, pedagogical innovation, considering technological and digital based learning environment, is a matter of integration among different levels of analysis, from individual to social, and from traditional to most innovative teaching and learning practices. The need for a better understanding of how people learn and how technologies need to be used to enhance this learning is also discussed, with a final part on how creativity and innovation have to face 'mundane' educational settings daily issues.

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Introduction

The presence of technology in learning environments (school, university, professional training, refresher courses etc.) does not necessarily entail a direct change in pedagogical vision or teaching practices. The mere placing of computers, video projectors and IWBs in classrooms does not mark the ultimate attainment of a teaching innovation. For this reason, we believe it important to discuss the concept of technology-based pedagogical innovation, connect this concept to a learning theory, clarify the role of technology as far as teachers and learning results are concerned and, thus, reflect on the different levels of analyses in the study of the relationship between technologies and results.

Pedagogical and technological innovation

With reference to recent research carried out within the scope of the European project Creative Classroom (Bocconi, Kampylis, and Punie, 2012), we can define pedagogical innovation as that set of products, processes, strategies and approaches which significantly improve the state of affairs, becoming reference points (Kampylis, Bocconi, and Punie, 2012). According to the Centre for Educational Research and Innovation (CERI), promoting innovation in the learning environment is not at all easy.

It is a task which requires great commitment, it usually requires the ability to manage multiple resistances (OECD/CERI, 2009), and it frequently translates into slow rates of

change. For example Fullan (2011) argues that, although in some countries laptops and video projectors are replacing blackboards and chalk, the majority of students continue to experience their traditional role as “consumers of information” rather than problem solvers, producers of information and innovators.

Innovating learning processes through technology involves a thorough renewal of the way we use and produce information and knowledge (Kampylis, Bocconi and Punie, 2012). This vision is opposed to the use of technologies to replicate traditional teaching practices. It can be extended to formal and informal learning environments, training adults, at school and at university.

The potential for innovation generated by technology does however require organisational, institutional and pedagogical changes. On a strictly pedagogical level we believe that a good starting point is the How People Learn (Donovan and Bransford, 2005) approach, recently referred to in the project Digital Learning Classroom (Lopez, 2010). The approach puts forward five general principles:

- Learners learn better when knowledge merges with and/or develops from what they already know
- Learners learn better when they work with others in learning, they ask questions and they reflect on what they have learnt and how it was learnt
- Learners learn better when the information offered and the context are tailored to the cognitive needs of them
- Learners learn better if what they learn is fundamental and in-depth and if the individual competences/abilities are strongly anchored to a principle/general concept, and if what they have studied has multiple applications
- Learners learn better when they are given feedback and/or are given the opportunity to evaluate their own learning.

The five principles offer a framework which is useful in designing learning solutions aimed at integrating technology into teaching (Gentile, 2012).

The IWB example

IWBs can be an important resource for involving pupils during lessons (Armstrong et al., 2005; Gentile, Pisanu, 2012; Greiffenhagen, 2000; Schmid, 2006; Wall, Higgins, and Smith, 2005). However, problems of a varying nature do materialise around them:

- An increase in the centrality of the teacher and a reduction in collaborative interaction amongst students can be observed (Latane, 2002; Jones and Tanner, 2002; Maor, 2003)
- Accelerated paces in lessons can be observed (Glover and Miller 2001), to the detriment of the quality of cognitive interaction between teachers and pupils (Smith, Hardman, and Higgins, 2006).

If used as static technology, the IWB does not produce any appreciable changes in teaching practices (Beauchamp, 2004; Glover, Miller, 2009). In other words, the technology alone does not encourage tout court more effective ways of teaching.

Technologies, computers and learning

Technologies can increase probabilities of learning. However, we cannot definitively state that there is a direct relationship between technologies and learning results. Evidence, in this regard, is contrasting.

Hattie (2009), when revising the meta-analyses regarding different types of

technologies found effects which varied from 0.09 of standard deviation² for distance learning up to a maximum of 0.52 of standard deviation associated with learning methods based on interactive videos. In more specific terms the meta-analyses show that computers are used effectively:

- When teachers use them as part of a variety of teaching strategies
- When there is preliminary training on how to use a computer as a teaching and learning tool
- When there are multiple learning opportunities
- When the student, not the teacher, controls learning in terms of timing, pace, material, choice of task, etc.
- When teachers are attentive to conditions for peer-learning
- When teachers are attentive to feedback.

Notwithstanding some conditions of use, technologies can influence the teaching/learning process, above all when they are centered on the students. Unfortunately it is just as clear that the impacts of technologies on learning outcomes have provided contrasting results. One of the main reasons for such an outcome may be related to the methodological issues. A large part of research, for example, does not differentiate the main effect of technologies from other possible effects associated with context and individual variables (CERI, 2010; Cox, Marshall, 2007).

In our opinion the levels to consider should include the following:

- School level: organisation of learning environments, presence and leadership on the part of the head teacher, peer-support etc.
- Technological level: devices (computers, iwbs, tablets, video-projectors, software, etc.)
- Teacher level: competence in using technology, training background in using technology, methods of teaching and class management, aims in using technology, etc.
- Student level: competence and frequency in using technology, gender, social-economic status or family background, psycho-social constructs like motivation or self-efficacy, etc.

Limiting our conclusions to the contents of this paper, the overview given above tells us that research follows a single-level logic and that the student level is still difficult for researchers to access, above all in Italy. Student data appear to be relevant and necessary in order to validate technological innovation through the measuring of learning results and educational outcomes. Our hope is that in the future attempts to consider more levels of analysis are made more frequently, above all in order to guide schools and teachers in technological integration in teaching.

A possible way of integration: The creative class room framework

This paper looks also at 'Creative Classrooms', focusing on their pedagogical, technological and organizational dimensions for innovation. Insights are from a European research project, carried out by EC JRC-IPTS from December 2011 to June 2013, on "Up-scaling Creative Classrooms in Europe" (SCALE CCR). Aim of the study is to provide a better understanding of ICT-enabled innovation for learning and to identify policy recommendations for the further mainstreaming of ICT in Education and Training (EandT) in Europe. In addition to desk research, a number of existing cases have been analyzed (eTwinning, Hellerup Skole, and Notschool.net) which provide insights on major enablers and barriers of CCR implementation in real contexts.

Main project results highlight the multi-dimensional and holistic nature of the Creative Classrooms as innovative learning environments that fully embed the potentials of ICT for learning. The model consists of eight encompassing and interconnected dimensions that capture the essential nature of these learning ecosystems: Content and Curricula, Assessment, Learning Practices, Teaching Practices, Organization, Leadership and Values, Connectedness, and Infrastructure. A set of reference parameters have been developed, for policymakers and practitioners, which depict the systemic approach that is needed for the sustainable implementation and progressive scaling-up of Creative Classrooms across Europe.

Conclusion

In the history of technology there is a reoccurring tendency to focus one's attention on the technical innovations of the new tools, to the detriment of pedagogical reflection and evaluation of sustainability. It's the concept of innovation which is ambiguous. We are conditioned by an inheritance of enlightenment according to which innovation = progress = improvement. If we bring technologies into schools, or in other different social environments, we are no doubt changing something, thus we can say that we are innovating. The problem is establishing whether this innovation brings about significant pedagogical 'improvement' or not (Calvani, 2012). In a recent work in the Italian context, Gentile and colleagues (2013) proposed a so called Learning Solution Approach (LSA). The LSA implies the design of learning activity intentionally focused on cognitive goals aligned to the national curriculum. In a LSA activity (LSAA), students recall knowledge, interact with software, carry out paper and pencil tasks (writing, reading, calculate), collaborate with classmates, reflect on how and what they learn. In this context, technology is one of the tools of learning mediation, not the only one. A LSAA has five components: contents, technology, cooperative tasks, formative assessment, feedback, in terms of peer-assessment and teachers' feedback.

In this paper, I have presented technologies as tools to support learning (Wall et al., 2005). For this reason, I think it is difficult to offer teachers guidance on how to use them without a clear understanding of how pupils learn (Howland et al., 2012). The LSA approach could be an attempt to support a integrated pedagogical ICT-based innovation starting from an incremental, rather than radical point of view (Cooper, 1998).

I believe that innovative project based on LSA might get the level of educational innovation, both at local and national level if it will help to develop a key focus on the following points. First, design and implementation of classroom-based solutions, which help teachers to integrate technology in subject-matter teaching and learning. Second, encourage an open use of hardware and software devices; provide pupils with lots of opportunities for learning. Last but not the least, ensure a consistent support to teachers during the instructional work.

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